

A Comparison Study on Trade Development and Comparative Advantages of BRICS Countries

Pak Yuliya^{1*}

¹School of Economics, Shanghai University, China

Abstract: This study implements a comparison analysis on trade development of BRICS union, focusing on comparative advantages of each participant. The Balassa index is employed for calculation of RCA values of BRICS participants for certain commodities so to identify their comparative advantages. The RCA calculations are conducted on HS2 and HS4 digit level data for the five BRICS countries. In order to maintain a track of changes in RCA values of BRICS countries across different time series, the years 2010, 2012, 2014, 2016 and 2019 are examined. The results of the article showed that all BRICS countries have a potential to expand trade relations between each other in the future. China will be able to expand trade relations with Russia, India and Brazil even more, if it will export to these countries such products as articles of apparel, new pneumatic tires, articles of wood and glassware. While, Brazil will be able to improve trade relations with Russia, China, India and South Africa by exporting to these countries copper, aluminum, zinc, oil seeds & oleaginous fruits, meat & edible meat offal and copper. It is suggested for Russia to export coal, petroleum oils, natural gas, copper and wood to India, Brazil and China. While, India has to focus more on exporting mostly pharmaceuticals to Russia, Brazil, China and South Africa. Finally, South Africa has potential to trade more with India, Brazil and China, if it will export there edible fruit and nuts, coal, iron & steel, pearls and coal.

Keywords: RCA, BRICS, Balassa Index, export structure, Ricardian theory.

*Corresponding Author: Pak Yuliya

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Introduction

First time Brazil, Russia, India and China were mentioned as BRIC in an analytical note of Goldman Sachs banks by an economist Jim O'neil. Jim O'neill, who was a chairman of Goldman Sachs at that time, predicted that in the future " the weight of the BRICs and especially China in the world GDP will grow, raising important issues about the global economic impact of fiscal and monetary policy in the BRICs". In this way, he estimated in the note that at end of 2000, GDP of BRIC based on PPP basis was about 23%(in US\$) of world GDP. China's GDP in 2001 was bigger than of Italy. Jim O'Neil expected the GDP of BRICs and especially China to grow for the next 10 years.

Since formation of the block, many economists were holding different opinions about it. Some of them were underlining the differences in economic structures, financial systems, political regimes, culture background, geopolitical position and geographical location. They were suggesting that the differences are too large, which can become an obstacle for successful cooperation. Whereas, others were holding an opinion that in spite of current contradictions between BRICS participants, they still will be able to find mutual interests of cooperation in the future. The five countries were expected to boost economically and financially in couple of decades. Therefore, it was fair to suppose that BRICS members had at least common necessities and aims in terms of facilitation the development of their economics.

After several years since BRICS formation, some studies have appeared about BRICS in economic and trade related studies (Chatterje, Jena and Singh, 2014; Mathur and Dasgupta, 2013; Sandrey and Jensen, 2007 or Sharma and Kallummal, 2012) and about FDI policy (Mlachila and Takebe, 2011).

Javeria Maryam, Umer Jeelanie Bandy, Ashok Mittal (2018) examined the intra-BRICS BRICS and BRICS-EU trade flows. They claimed that there are large bilateral trade flows among BRICS members. Eventually, they come to the point that Russia was the main trading partner with EU in BRICS. Moreover, according to similarity index there is a presence of competition between India and China in EU.

Libo Wu, Xoangshuo Yin, Changhe Li, Haoqi Qian, Taoran Chen and Weiqi Tang claimed in their paper "Trade and investment among BRICS" that a promotion of economy openness in BRICS countries, will increase their aggregate economy level along with export's volume, especially in case of China and Russia. At the same time, tariff reduction and elimination of trade barriers can cause unbalanced growth results, what can influence trade balances of BRICS countries negatively. They employed such tools as CGE model for the analyses of the effects of free trade on BRICS countries.

Bohdan Vahalik and Michaela Stanikova studied key factors of foreign trade competitiveness between EU and BRICS by the application of factor and cluster analyses (2016). The study was based on the World Bank's (Farole et al. 2010) Trade Competitiveness Diagnostic Toolkit. The paper concluded that competitiveness of territory resides not only in competitiveness of its constituent individual entities and their interactions, but also in the wider assets and social economic, institutional and public attributes of the country itself.

Theories regarding RCA index

RCA index is based on Ricardian theory. The index shows a ratio of product's share (industry) in national sector to the share in the world export. The index is called "revealed", because calculations are conducted based on already revealed data about export. A comparative advantage is considered to be "revealed" if $RCA > 1$. If a nation has a revealed comparative advantage for a certain product, then this country is considered to be a competitive producer and exporter of a given product relative to a partner country with $RCA < 1$. It can be said that at the beginning of BRICS union formation, it was more perceived as a political block. At the same time, on the first stages, BRICS was developing more in geopolitical direction. However, later on, more and more scholar works related to trade of BRICS countries began to appear. There were various tools and approaches used in order to analyze BRICS from trade perspective, including Panel-Gravity model, similarity index, CGE model, factor and cluster analyses and others. Some studies concluded that manufactured products and raw material trade integration of Russia is different from that of other BRICS members.

While, others found out, Russia was the main trading partner with EU in BRICS. There were also such outcomes as that a promotion of economy openness in BRICS countries, will increase their aggregate economy level along with export's volume, especially in case of China and Russia. Following the previous researches, it can be said, that there is an interest to study trade relations inside BRICS union and outside BRICS union.

Research Methodology

The RCA calculations for each of BRICS participant are conducted on HS2 and HS4 digit level data. This article employed the data for 2010, 2012, 2014, 2016 and 2019 years to maintain a track of changes in RCA values of BRICS countries across different time series. The RCA index also called Balassa index was applied to calculate the relative advantage for certain groups of products, which were chosen individually for each of BRICS member considering their economic development and changes in export structure over time. The Balassa index is calculated according to the following formula:

$$RCA_i = (X_{i,j} / \sum x_j) / (X_{i,World} / \sum X_{World})$$

The major shortcomings of the RCA Index is its asymmetric property. The RCA Index has a fixed lower bound of 0 with 1 being the comparative advantage neutral point, while its upper bound in general is not delimited as seen in Figure 1:

Fig.1: Range of the RCA Index

As the theoretical range of RCA index was too broad, Hinloopen and van Marrewijk (2001) suggested an auxiliary interpretational categories to the distribution of the RCA index. Hinloopen and van Marrewijk (2001) continued to divide the theoretical range of the RCA Index into four additional classes depicted in Table1. These four classes illustrate the strength of a country's comparative advantage.

Table 1: The classes of comparative advantage

Table 1: The States of Comparative Advantage		
Class	Value of RCA	Result index
Class A	0-1	Industries with comparative disadvantage
Class B	1-2	Industries with weak comparative advantage
Class C	2-4	Industries with medium comparative advantage
Class D	Greater than 4	Industries with strong comparative advantage

Source: Hinloopen and Marrewijk (2001)

Comparison of Brazil's RCA with BRICS

Table 2: Comparison of Brazil's RCA with BRICS

No	Year	Brazil's RCA	Russia's RCA	India's RCA	China's RCA	South Africa's RCA	Year
	Product						
	Non-ferrous metals						
1	Copper ores and concentrates	3.2	0.20	0.40	0.00	0.8	2019

2	Nickel ores and concentrates	0.00	5.7	0.2	0.00	0.01	
3	Aluminium ores and concentrates	16.1	0.2	2.1	0.18	0.04	
4	Lead ores and concentrates	0.24	1.09	3.4	0.10	1.05	2019
5	Zinc ores and concentrates	1.2	0.05	2.08	0.40	0.1	2019
5	Coal, whether or not pulverized, not agglomerated	0.00	6.2	0.04	0.07	8.8	2019
6	Oil seeds and oleaginous fruits; miscellaneous grains, seeds and fruit;	29	0.4	0.97	0.08	0.04	2019
9	Meat and edible meat offal	3.7	0.23	0.00	0.71	0.50	2019
10	Coffee, whether or not roasted or decaffeinated	11.5	0.19	1.25	0.10	0.18	2019
11	Cocoa	0.76	0.02	0.14	0.02	0.02	2019
12	Chocolate, food preparations with cocoa, n.e.s.	0.28	1.04	0.25	0.08	0.48	2019
13	Tea, whether or not flavoured	0.75	0.5	5.5	1.35	0.62	2019
15	Tobacco, manufactured	0.23	0.65	0.68	0.22	1.17	2019
16	Iron ore and concentrates	15.3	0.74	1.11	0.03	9.8	2019

In general, Brazil does not have matching RCA that much with other BRICS countries. Mainly if Brazil has RCA for some commodities, then other BRICS countries do not have RCA for these products. In addition, Brazil has similar RCA with some of BRICS countries only for certain products rather than for an entire sector or industry as in case with China. Compare with four BRICS countries, Brazil has similar RCA mostly with India for such products as meat, coffee, spices, tobacco and iron. Whereas with Russia and China, Brazil does not have similar RCA at all in the presented table. Regarding South Africa, Brazil has similar RCA with this country for spices and iron. In this way, it can be said that Brazil is supposed to have intense trade relations with all BRICS countries, especially with China and Russia.

Comparison of Russia's RCA with BRICS

Table 3: Comparison of Russia's RCA with BRICS

№	Year	Russia's RCA	Brazil's RCA	India's RCA	China's RCA	South Africa's RCA	Year
	Product						
	Cereals, unmilled(excl.wheat, rice, barley, maize)	0.94	0.23	1.28	0.14	0.58	2019
	Coal; briquettes, ovoids and similar solid fuels manufactured from coal	6.26	0.00	0.04	0.07	8.8	2019
	Petroleum oils and oils obtained from bituminous minerals, crude	4.01	0.66	3.36	0.33	0.80	2019
	Liquefied propane and butane	1.07	2.65	0.00	0.10	0.15	2019
	Natural gas, liquefied	1.87	2.13	0.01	0.03	0.00	2019
	Copper ores and concentrates	0.22	3.2	0.4	0.00	0.8	2019
	Nickel ores and concentrates	5.7	0.00	0.2	0.00	0.01	2019
	Aluminium ores and concentrates	0.2	16.1	2.1	0.18	0.04	2019
	Lead ores and concentrates	1.09	0.24	3.4	0.10	1.05	2019
	Zinc ores and concentrates	0.05	1.23	2.08	0.04	0.10	2019

	Wood and articles of wood; wood charcoal	1.85	1.57	0.00	0.00	3.87	2019
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In overall, Russia mostly has RCA for the same products with South Africa, what can be explained by the fact that both countries depend on natural resources and mainly specialize in exporting of raw materials. The countries have common RCA in crude fertilizers, coal, copper, nickel, aluminum, lead and wood.

Russia and China do not have similar RCA in any products in the presented table, except for aluminum in which China has a weak comparative advantage (0.92). Regarding Brazil and India, with these two countries, Russia has the same RCA only for several products. Following comparison results, it can be supposed that Russia and China can have the most developed trade relations among four countries. China's GDP is second biggest in the world after USA now, the country's manufacturing sector continues to expand rapidly. That is why China is in a big need for raw materials and primary products, for most of which, Russia has big reserves. However, Russia has opportunity to develop trade with India and Brazil too as these two countries do not have comparative advantage for most of those products in which Russia has. Based on comparison of Russia's RCA with south Africa, it can be seen that these two countries do not have much of potential of establishing intense trade relations. First of all, Russia and South Africa have the same RCA for many products. Secondly, both countries have not developed their manufacturing sectors that much by today. Thirdly, due to large distance between the two countries, transportation cost will be too high and it will be more profitable for both countries to trade with nearby countries rather than with each other. In this way, Russia and South Africa do not have foundation for mutually-beneficial exchange with products.

Comparison of India's RCA with BRICS

Table 4: Comparison of India's RCS with BRICS

№	Year	India's RCA	Russia's RCA	China	Brazil's RCA	South Africa's RCA	Year
	Product						
1	Natural or cultured pearls, precious or semi-precious stones, precious metals, metals clad...	10.31	1.30	0.10	0.13	2.62	2019
2	Sugars and sugar confectionery	3.8		0.27			
3	Rice	16.6		0.25			
4	Crustaceans, mollusks and aquatic invertebrates, prepared or preserved (excluding smoked)	8.99	0.36	1.14	0.00	0.72	2019
5	Cotton	3.80	0.00	0.02	12.6	0.77	2019
6	Coffee, whether or not roasted or decaffeinated; coffee skins; coffee substitutes...	1.25	0.19	0.10	11.5	0.18	2019
	Cocoa	0.14	0.02	0.02	0.76	0.02	2019
	Chocolate, food preparations with cocoa, n.e.s.	0.25	1.04	0.08	0.28	0.48	2019
	Tea, whether or not flavoured	5.53	0.50	1.35	0.75	0.62	2019
	Pharmaceutical products	2.18	0.06	0.08	0.19	0.18	2019

The comparison table shows that two countries have comparative advantage in all commodities of articles of apparel sector, including men's clothing, women's clothing, men's or boy's clothing and clothing excluding textile. Degree of comparative advantage in the apparel sector between the two countries are almost the same, varies from weak

comparative advantage till middle comparative advantage. In addition China as well has RCA in tea and crustaceans, however India's RCA for these products is in group of strong comparative advantage, while China's is in group of weak comparative advantage. Despite the fact that China and India have comparative advantage for articles of apparel, India specializes in this sector at the greatest level compare to China. Nevertheless, India and China have comparative advantage for many commodities in the presented table, there are also more several commodities for which China does not have RCA and India does have. For example, cotton(3.8), coffee(1.2) and spices(11.7).

India have RCA only for couple of products with Brazil, Russia and South Africa. For all other products in the presented table, these three countries do not have comparative advantage. In this way, India has an opportunity to export such commodities as sea products, cotton (except Brazil), articles of apparel, coffee(except Brazil), cocoa and chocolate as well as medicinal and pharmaceutical items to Russia, Brazil and South Africa. However, articles of apparel is not a sophisticated product, which would be hard to produce and for these three countries will be much more profitable to export them from other countries too. The sea products are also would be better to export from nearby countries rather than from India. Regarding trade with Russia, Brazil and South Africa, it would be best for India to focus in pharmaceutical industry

Comparison of South Africa's RCA with BRICS

Table 5: Comparison of South Africa's RCA with BRICS

No	Year	South Africa's RCA	India'sRCA	Brazil's RCA	Russia's RCA	China's RCA	Year
	Product						
1	Gold, incl.gold plated with platinum, unwrought or not further worked than semi-manufactured...	3.04	0.02	0.92	0.77	0.02	2019
2	Jewellery & articles of precious material., n.e.s.	0.24	6.07	0.10	0.07	6.07	2019
3	Aluminium	0.04	2.14	16.1	2.02	0.92	2019
4	Natural or cultured pearls, precious or semi-precious stones, precious metals, metals clad...	2.62	10.3	0.13	1.30	0.10	2019
5	Coal; briquettes, ovoids and similar solid fuels manufactured from coal	8.82	0.04	0.00	6.26	0.07	2019
6	Edible fruit and nuts; peel of citrus fruit or melons	5.65	0.66	0.60	0.03	0.37	2019

In overall, South Africa have similar RCA with India, Brazil and Russia in the sector of iron and steel. Unexpectedly, South Africa have similar RCA mostly with India, there are 10 commodities for which both countries have the same RCA in the presented table. Those commodities include pearls, pig iron, ingots, flat-rolled iron, steel bars, wire of iron or steel, fruits, stones, natural abrasives and other crude minerals. There are three commodities in which South Africa and China have similar RCA, including iron, fruits and other crude minerals. In this way it can be supposed that South Africa and China has a big potential of developing trade relations. First of all, South Africa owns considerable amount of natural reserves, which China does not have, Secondly, China is in a big need for those natural resources due to fact that its economy develops very rapidly now. In turn, South Africa can import from China manufactured products as it was already mentioned earlier.

As comparison results showed, Brazil can export oil seeds&oleaginous fruits, meat&edible meat offal to Russia; copper to India; aluminum, zinc and copper to China and edible meat offal to South Africa. While, Russia should expand trade

with such commodities as coal, petroleum oils and natural gas with Brazil and coal with China; gas, copper and wood with Russia and petroleum oils with South Africa. In order to improve the trade within BRICS union, India should export pharmaceutical products, sugar and rice to China and pharmaceutical products to Russia; cotton and pharmaceutical products to South Africa. However, there is very small possibility to increase trade between India and Brazil, because Brazil does not have demand for products India has $RCA < 1$ for. Next, China can expand the trade with BRICS participants more, if it exports articles of apparel to Brazil, new pneumatic tires to Russia as well as articles of wood and glassware to China. Regarding South Africa, China already exports two products for which it has $RCA < 1$, these are electrical machinery and mechanical appliances. According comparison results of Chapter 6, it was suggested to China to not export any other products beside the two mentioned above as South Africa does not have demand for other products China has comparative advantage for in Table 5. Finally, it was found out, South Africa has well developed trade relations only with China among other four BRICS participants. So, South Africa can export more edible fruit and nuts to India, gold to Russia, coal and iron&steel to Brazil and also pearls and coal to China.

In comparison of China's RCA with other four BRICS countries, it can be seen that Russia and South Africa have the least amount of the similar RCAs with China. It can be seen in the presented table that Russia does not have comparative advantage for any of manufactured goods(except manufactures of wood), electrical machinery, specialized machinery or other industrial machinery. This reveals a gap in economy of Russia. Back to earlier section of this paper, it was discussed that Russia has been relying too much on reserves of natural resources, which put the development of its manufacturing section into stagnation. Similar situation is with Brazil and South Africa, while Brazil still have RCA in the presented table, South Africa have RCA only for several products.

In this way, China is supposed to trade most intensively with Russia, Brazil and South Africa in contrast with India. It is beneficial for Brazil to import from China the commodities from manufacturing sector as well as electrical machinery products, specialized machinery products and other industrial machinery products. India can import from China electrical machinery commodities, specialized machinery commodities and other industrial commodities. For Russia it would be beneficial to import from China commodities from manufactured sector (except veneers), electrical machinery, specialized machinery, other industrial machinery and also silk . Finally South Africa also can export all those products for which China has RCA except for pottery, civil engineering, food-processing machines and pumps for liquids. In overall, China is supposed to have a dominant position in BRICS regarding trade, because its manufactured sector is highly developed by now, while the rest four countries mainly specialize in other sectors of economies. In addition, China needs more of natural resources which other four BRICS countries do have, this point will be discussed in more detail in the following sections.

Table 5: Comparison of China's RCA with BRICS

No	Country/year	China's RCA	Brazil's RCA	India's RCA	Russia's RCA	South Africa's RCA	Year
	Product						
	Rice	0.25	1.29	16.6	0.14	0.57	2019
1	Silk	5.14	0.16	1.3	0.00	0.00	2019
	Manufactured goods						2019
3	Articles of leather; saddlery and harness; travel goods, handbags and similar containers; articles...	1.79	0.17	2.68	0.02	0.37	2019
4	Articles of apparel and clothing accessories, knitted or crocheted	2.17	0.02	2.08	0.03	0.12	2019
5	New pneumatic tyres, of rubber	1.44	1.22	1.36	0.62	0.64	2019
6	Articles of rubber, n.e.s.	0.76	0.44	1.16	0.18	0.70	2019
7	Cork manufactures	0.11	0.01	0.10	0.04	0.07	2019
9	Wood and articles of wood; wood charcoal	2.19	1.11	0.51	0.53	0.58	2019
10	Paper and paperboard	0.64	1.30	0.84	0.84	0.70	2019
12	Woven fabrics of cotton	4.20	0.32	3.72	0.07	0.22	2019
13	Glass and glassware	1.54	0.24	0.37	0.43	0.42	2019
17	Furniture and parts thereof. n.e.s. (excluding seats and medical, surgical, dental or...)	2.49	0.31	0.49	0.1	0.29	2019
18	Footwear, gaiters and the like; parts of such articles	2.53	0.60	1.08	0.08	0.22	2019
19	Baby carriages, toys, games&sporting goods	3.7	0.01	0.2	0.07	0.1	2019
20	Electrical machinery and equipment and parts thereof;	1.99	0.23	1.14	0.09	0.22	2019
21	Machinery, mechanical appliances, nuclear reactors, boilers; parts thereof	2.81	0.10	0.13	0.34	0.32	2019

Discussion

The analysis results for China and BRICS showed, China has mutual trade relations on high level with each of BRICS countries. However, there still certain commodities were found out, with which BRICS countries can improve their trade relations even more. In order to increase trade development, Brazil can import from China articles of apparel, while Russia can import from China new pneumatic tires and India should import articles of wood and glassware.

While, analysis results for Brazil and BRICS showed, out of four countries Brazil has well developed trade relations only with China, both countries export and import from each other in big amounts. However, with the rest three

countries Brazil's trade development on is low. Hence, based on RCA calculations there are certain commodities are suggested for trade.

Nevertheless, China's import volume is already big, Brazil can export to China copper, aluminum and zinc so to increase their trade development even more. At the same time, Brazil can export oil seeds&oleaginous fruits and meat&edible meat offal to Russia as the country has a high demand for these products. Next, Brazil should export copper to India and meat and edible meat offal to South Africa.

Similar to Brazil, out of four BRICS countries, Russia trade intensively only with China, while with the rest three countries the trade level had been remaining very low for a long time. In order to increase trade with Brazil, Russia can export to it coal, petroleum oils and natural gas as Brazil has a high demand for this product. Whereas, Russia can export gas, copper and wood to India and petroleum oils to SA. Also, to increase trade with China even more, Russia can export coal to China.

India also has the most intense trade relations only with China out of four BRICS countries. In order to intensify the trade relations with Brazil and Russia, India can export pharmaceuticals to them as both countries have a high demand for these two commodities. While, South Africa is in demand for cotton and pharmaceutical products, so India can export these two products to it. Regarding China, India can export pharmaceutical products, sugar and rice to this country.

South Africa trades intensively only with China too out of four BRICS countries. It was said that India has a high demand for edible fruit and nuts, so South Africa can export exactly this commodity to it. Also, South Africa can export coal and iron&steel to Brazil. Regarding China, South Africa can export pearls and coal to it.

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